

FORMATION OF NEOLOGISMS BY THE PREFIXAL METHOD (ON THE MATERIAL OF THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)

R. R. Biksaliyeva

Navoi Innovation Institute, Navoi, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7581337>

Abstract. *The article discusses the formation of neologisms in the prefix way in the Russian and Uzbek languages. The semantics of the most used foreign language prefixes, the scope of use and the peculiarities of functioning in these areas are analyzed.*

Keywords: *comparative study, multi-system languages, foreign language prefixes, derivational-semantic space of language, neologisms.*

Comparative study of word formation in different system languages, like many other topical areas of modern linguistics, began at the end of the 20th and beginning of the 21st century and has now received a new impetus for its development. Harmonious correlation of principles of the system- and anthropocentrism of the comparison of derivatologists at the output of a new level of generalizations is acceptable for objects and results of word-formation determination, taking into account the prism of linguistic consciousness and specific linguistic cultures.

Interlingual comparative analysis of different types of word-building units opens up new perspectives for derivatological science and linguistics in general. It helps to better characterize the formal and semantic structure of the derivative word and complex word-formation units, as well as their role in the process of language nomination. Until recently, binary comparison of word-formation systems was carried out most often in the formal-structural and structural-semantic aspects, since the existing similarities and differences are found primarily at the level of word-formants and word-formation methods.

The current interest in the content side of word-formation processes, the analysis of the derivational-semantic space of the language make it possible to obtain information about some features of the nominative cognitive activity of a person, namely “to specify the structure of knowledge embedded in the derived word” [1, p. 393].

When considering the active processes of word formation in the late 20th - early 21st centuries, researchers pay attention to the central role of prefixation. Prefixing does not significantly change the lexical meaning, but only modifies the semantics of the root. Also, the prefix does not have a significant impact on the grammatical characteristics of the original lexeme. Therefore, prefixes mainly perform a word-formation function, participating in the formation of new words. Prefixes introduce evaluative semantics into neoplasms.

Having analyzed the dictionary of word-building affixes of the modern Russian language V.V. Lopatina and I.S. Ulukhanov [2] and the media on the issue of prefixing neologisms, about 100 new prefix innovations created with the help of foreign prefixes were noted. The word formation of neologisms is quite extensive, but verbs are subject to the most active prefixation, since most of the verbal prefixes are polysemantic and express different types of meanings (spatial, temporal, quantitative, for example: in, on, by, s, y), while in adjectives and In nouns, each prefix usually expresses one or two meanings.

As we know, prefixes are divided into foreign and native Russian. Depending on the quality of the assessment, prefixes can be divided into negative and positive in terms of semantics. The affixes with a possible negative appraisal include the foreign language prefix anti- with the meaning of negation. With the help of this morpheme, substantives are formed with the semantics “something opposite, opposed to or directed against what is called a motivating noun” [1,44]: Anti-record (title). Uzbekistan has updated the anti-record for the number of cases of COVID-19 infection per day! (“Gazeta.UZ”. 26.05.21) ← anti- + record; Anti-rating: regions-debtors for electricity are named in Uzbekistan (headline) (“Sputniknews.uz”, 24.11.20) ← anti- + rating; Anti-award "Trump and Travolta nominated for anti-award" (headline). (“Sputniknews.uz”. 21.01.19) ← anti- + premium. As can be seen from the examples, the prefix derivatives anti-record, anti-rating, anti-premium lose their positive connotation and become negatively evaluated derivatives. Thus, neoplasms with the prefix anti change the sign of the original word to polar, acquire a negative-evaluative connotation in the microcontext.

The use of neologisms in both Russian and Uzbek is widespread and is used in most cases in the media, newspapers and magazines. Prefixes with negative semantics are used in magazines to influence the reader. So, words with the prefix de- / de- with the semantics “action, opposite, opposite to the action called the motivating noun” [2, p. 71].

Also in the Uzbek language “deideologizatsiya”: One of the principles of the “Uzbek model” of national development, “deideologization” as an ideology, certainly played a positive role in building a sovereign democratic state of law in the radical revival of society” [5]: The prefix post-/post- introduces meaning: existing, occurring after what is called the motivating word. Compare: post-perestroika, post-referendum, post-editor; post muharriri, postindustrial etc.

Ameliorative expressiveness is typical for neoplasms with the super- prefix with the semantics “someone who has (s) to the highest or high degree the signs of being (who) is called (o) a motivating noun (sometimes with a shade: main in relation to that who is called a motivating noun)” [2, p. 229]: super action movie, superpower, supercar, super prize; supermodel, superinfeksiya, superkompyuter, supermatn.

Interest in "Americanization" contributed to the increase in the word-building activity of the new prefix mega-/mega- with the meaning "high degree of quality": megaarena, mega-action, megaproject, mega-corruption.

As rightly noted by T.B. Radbil and L.V. Ratsiburskaya, “the size-evaluative prefixes super-/super-, hyper-/giper, ultra-/ultra, mega-/mega-, etc., being active in derivational processes based not only on borrowed, but also native words, demonstrate such a feature, inherent in the Russian mentality, as a setting for the hypertrophy of the general, moral or aesthetic assessment in the nomination of persons, objects and events (“moral passion”, according to A. Vezhbitskaya)” [4, p. 36].

The tendency to save language means is reflected by the prefix ex- with the semantics “previously the one who (what) is called (o) a motivating noun” [2, p. 239]. This morpheme is actively used with words indicating social status or title, but in recent decades it can also be combined with words denoting a person by profession, occupation, marital status: ex-producer, ex-colleague. Under the influence of the context, the prefix ex- can form expressive negative evaluative neoplasms: ex-wife, ex-vice-president, ex-premier, ex-deputy prime minister / eks-president, eks-spiker.

The given examples show that the effectiveness of prefix word formation as a means of influence lies in the use of various communication strategies (evaluation strategy, discrediting strategy) and speech tactics (antipathy expression tactics, negative illustration tactics, self-elevation tactics). With their help, journalists generate appraisal and a powerful expressive effect, inspire desired attitudes in the objects of influence, concentrate their attention on certain meanings.

REFERENCES

1. Kubryakova E.S. Language and knowledge: On the way to gaining knowledge about language: Parts of speech from a cognitive point of view. The role of language from the point of view of understanding the world / Russian Academy of Sciences. Institute of Linguistics. - M.: Languages of Slavic Culture, 2004.-560s.
2. Lopatin B.B. , Ulukhanov I.S. . Dictionary of word-building affixes of the modern Russian language. M.: Publishing Center "Azbukovnik", 2016. 812 p.
3. Popova T.B. Russian Neology and Neography: educational electronic text edition. Yekaterinburg: GOU VPO USTU-UPI, 2005. 96 p.
4. Radbil T.B., Ratsiburskaya L.V. Word-building innovations based on borrowed elements in the modern Russian language: linguoculturological aspect // The World of the Russian Word. 2017. No. 2. P. 33–39.
5. Article. The ideological foundations of building a democratic society. URL: <https://www.test-uz.ru/articles.php?id=1077>